

ONCE AGAIN ABOUT THE ORIGIN OF THE TOPONYM KAMCHATKA

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Annotation. There is extensive literature and a large number of hypotheses about the origin of the toponym, Kamchatka. These are analyzed in detail by the historian, B. P. Polevoy, in his work “New About the Discovery of Kamchatka”. This hypothesis has been criticized by a number of authors. We have analyzed publications on the development of Northeast Asia by Russia in the 17th century, associated with Kamchatka and archival documents of the Russian State Archive of Ancient Acts (RGADA). We have published a new look about the forgotten hypothesis of A. N. Bondareva, about the Yakut roots of the toponym “Kamchatka” is published on the basis of the original documents of the Russian State Archive of Ancient Acts (petition of the foreman Ivan Rubets, etc.) and an attempt is made to understand the etymology of the word Kamchatka, its connection with the Yakut word “khamcha” (in Yakut - a smoking pipe).

Keywords: Toponymy, Kamchatka, petition of the Cossack Ivan Rubets, Semyon Dezhnev, Fedot Popov, Yakut wife of Fedot Popov, “khamcha”, smoking pipe

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Introduction. There is extensive literature and a large number of hypotheses about the origin of the toponym, Kamchatka. These are analyzed in detail by the historian, B. P. Polevoy, in his work “New About the Discovery of Kamchatka”, published in 1997 by the publishing house, “Kamchatskiy Pechatny Dvor,” in Petropavlovsk-Kamchatskiy. In this book, the author substantiated his hypothesis about the origin of the toponym, Kamchatka, on behalf of the Cossack explorer, I. I. Kamchaty. But, unfortunately, the author did not find direct historical documents confirming his point of view [1]. This hypothesis has been criticized by a number of authors [2, 3, 4]. We have published a new look about the forgotten hypothesis of A. N. Bondareva, about the Yakut roots of the toponym. The author, noting that “... in the languages of the indigenous peoples, there are no

words that could be brought closer to the word, Kamchatka without any exaggeration (there were many such attempts!),” connects the toponym with the Yakut word “Kamchaakkytan,” which are often mentioned in Yakut folklore [4] ... The form of the word given by A. N. Bondareva, is a derivative of the stem of the unchangeable part of the word “Khamchaakky” [5], “Khamchaakky” [6]. In this work, we have made an attempt to understand the etymology of the word Kamchatka, its connection with the Yakut word “khamcha” (in Yakut - smoking pipe), pronounced out of surprise by the Yakut wife of the merchant, Popov, when the smoking hill, Klyuchevskaya, appeared, when the Popov-Ankudinov company sailed through to an unknown river.

Methods and Materials. We have analyzed publications on the development of Northeast Asia by Russia

in the 17th century, associated with Kamchatka. Materials on the development of North-Eastern Siberia and Kamchatka, as well as contacts with the indigenous population of the region were collected from published literary sources and links, as well as from archival sources (RGADA). In addition, we analyzed the existing literature on the study of the origin of the word, Kamchatka. According to the data of archival materials and archaeological research, the period of the spread of tobacco and smoking pipes across the territory of North-Eastern Siberia has been clarified. Etymological studies of the Yakut word “khamcha, khamcha” were carried out according to various literary sources published in available literature.

Results. We find the first information about the passage of the Bering Strait and the likelihood of the first visit to Kamchatka by ser-

vice and industrial people of Russia back in 1648. At the initiative of the clerk of Moscow's merchants, Fedot Alekseev Popov (nicknamed Kholmogorov, since he was from Kholmogory), in 1648, an expedition was organized with the aim of discovering new lands and searching for sea routes to the Anadyr River, trade with the Chukchi and fishing for walrus bones. Fedot Popov financed the campaign, which is evident from the fact that he took with him 3,500 rubles and a lot of goods from the merchant, Usov [7]. He invited Semyon Dezhnev to organize and guard the campaign, collect taxes and be a representative of the authorities. It is known that Fedot Alekseev Popov took his Yakut wife with him (unfortunately, her name is unknown), and also allowed the Cossack, Gerasim Ankinin, to join the detachment. This brave Yakut woman, (she may have been a servant, yet this does not detract from her merits) together with her husband, S. Dezhnev, and her comrades rounded the Bolshoi Kamenny Nose and became the discoverers of the Bering Strait. Having rounded the cape, one by one the ships of the explorers crashed, first the ship of Ankinin, then Dezhnev. Popov and Dezhnev's teams lost contact with each other. Traces of Popov and Ankinin were discovered only in 1654. In the same year, S. Dezhnev wrote: "... I, Semeyka, on a campaign near the sea, and I, Semeyka, forcibly took away from the Koryaks a Yakut woman who was the kept woman of the merchant Fedot Popov." In the words of this long-suffering woman: "... Fedot and the serviceman, Yerasim, died of scurvy, and some comrades were beaten and several people remained, together they ran with only one soul (that is, without

anything), I don't know where" [8].

Dezhnev "crushed" the "Yakutka" in 1654, which means that she was in captivity by the Koryaks for 4 years. Miller's version of this story is interesting. He writes: "At the same time, Dezhnev went out, visiting the seashores, to the Koryak dwellings, where he saw a Yakut woman who had previously lived with Fedot Alekseev. This woman told him that Fedot Alekseev and Gerasim Ankinin had died of scurvy, and their other comrades had been beaten, while the few that were left fled to who knows where in boats. This is explained later in the news found in Kamchatka. For the few people who were not far from Fedot Alekseev, following in good weather near the sea shore to the south, finally came to the Kamchatka River, on which they established their residence, and, therefore, for the first of the Russians, those who settled in these places were honored" [7]. Further Miller writes: "... many years ago a certain Fedotov (perhaps the son of Fedot Alekseev) lived with them with his comrades at the mouth of the Nikula River, which the Russians therefore called Fedotovka. Kamchadals revered them as if they were gods and did not think that a human hand could harm them" [7].

Researchers were divided over the location where Fedot Alekseev Popov's team landed after the divergence with Dezhnev. Some believed Miller [7] and Spassky [9], and believed that they really went inland along the Kamchatka River, rounded Kamchatka and lived out their life on the Tigil River [10], while others believe that they moored near the mouth of the Anadyr [1].

The historian, B. Polevoy, believes that the Popovs did not have children [1]. It turns out that an un-

known Yakut woman is a participant in the discovery of not only the Bering Strait, but also the Kamchatka Peninsula, and is also the first witness of a meeting with Alaskan residents of the Eskimos on two islands opposite the Big Stone Nose. So, according to S. Dezhnev's formal reply: "And on those islands the Chukchi live, and their teeth are cut, their lips are cut, and the bone is a fish's tooth" [8]. Dezhnev, in his formal reply, apparently mistakenly considered the inhabitants of the two islands to be Chukchi. Most likely, these are Eskimos, they have a custom of decorating their lips with walrus teeth [11]. Apparently, this unknown Yakut woman gave the name to the largest river of the peninsula - Kamchatka. From the Kamchatka River you can see the steaming hill Klyuchevskaya, reminiscent of the Yakut steaming "khamcha" (women can pronounce this word in a flirtatious form as "khamcha"¹), from the surprise uttered by our heroine the word "khamcha". Probably her companions named the river along which they sailed Kamchatka. For example, how from the word "Chukchi" arose the designation of the Chukotka Peninsula. It should be noted that a similar hypothesis was put forward by N. A. Bondareva, who believed that the word Kamchatka originated from the Yakut "Khamchakkytan" [4]. The form of the word given by A. N. Bondareva is a derivative from the stem of the unchangeable part of the word "Khamchaakki" [5], "Khamchaki" [6], that is, the Yakut name of Kamchatka mentioned in folklore. None of the researchers took this hypothesis seriously, but in vain [1]. Returning to Dezhnev's listing, we note that for some reason he does not name any more information about Popov and Ankinin, their

¹ In academic dictionaries, this word is usually written as "khamcha", but in the colloquial dialect, there is undoubtedly a pronunciation of the word as "khamcha".

route, how they hibernated, about trades, what animals lived in these parts, a description of the big river, etc. Apparently, Dezhnev considered this information secret and did not disclose it openly. We assume that Dezhnev reported more detailed information about the questioning of Popov's wife to the local authorities in the city of Yakutsk. We find indirect evidence in the publications of the historian B.P. Polevoy [1, 12].

In his monograph "New About the Discovery of Kamchatka," Polevoy analyzes all the existing hypotheses of the origin of the toponym, "Kamchatka" and comes to the conclusion that the most acceptable is Efimov's hypothesis, the origin of the name, "Kamchatka," from damask fabric. But the absence of an example of toponyms in world practice from the name of the fabric casts doubt on this hypothesis. He himself suggests that this word probably originated from the name of the Cossack, Ivan Kamchaty. The author admits that not only the Cossack, Ivan Kamchaty and others were in Kamchatka, but, unfortunately, he did not find any direct indications of historical documents. The first document indicating Kamchatka was found in the archives of the TsGADA, B.P. Polevoy in 1961, filed by the Cossack, I. E. Rubets. We found this document in the archives of the Russian State Archive of Ancient Acts [13]. Its full text:

"(L. 138) To the Tsar and Grand Duke Alexei Mikhailovich, all the Great and Small and White Russia to the autocrat, your servant of the Yakutsk prison of the Cossacks is beating the head of your servant

Ivashko Merkuriev. I was your servant, in your great sovereign service behind the Nose. And I, your servant, took the top of the Komchatka River at the pogrom, your servant, a small Koryak and brought it with me to Yakutskaya. Merciful Tsar and Grand Duke Alexei Mikhailovich, all the Great and Small and White Russia the autocrat, perhaps my servant, led me, sir, to write down that little one. Tsar sovereign, have mercy, perhaps.

On L. 138 about. note: on December 177 at the 14th day will question and write.

(L. 139) And those same days before the surroundings and governor, before the prince, Ivan Petrovich Boryatinsky, and before the clerk, Stepan Yelchukov, the small, whom Ivashko Rubets brought in the order to the note, interrogated where he was taken², and in which year, and who took *his*³ name, and what kind he, and what is his name, and is not the son of a Taxes father?

And during the interrogation, the boy told the Koryak family, not the son of a yasak father, but took de *his* Ivashko Rubets during the pogrom with the Cossacks on the river in Kamchatka, but he did not remember what his name was in Koryak. And to this day he was not baptized, but called de *his* Ivashko Rubets by the Russian name Petrushka, and that is why de *his* is still called that name. And he does not remember how many years he was taken in the pogrom.

And in omens that small round-faced, flat-nosed, two upper teeth are missing, Russian hair, small growth.

According to the regulations of

LL. 138-139 and after articles L. 139: On December 177, on the 14th day, according to the sovereign's decree of the surroundings and waring Prince Ivan Petrovich Boryatinsky ordered that little one, if he was not a Yasashka, to write off in books for Ivashko and take the duty. On L. 139 about. note: on December 177, on the 14th day, that little Koryak family, Petrushka, was given to him, Ivashka, from the village hut. On L. 139 about. and after the text on L. 139 assault: to these interrogation speeches instead of the small Petrushka of Koryak, at his behest, the foreman Senka Apeshev put his handlived; For this note, I, Ivashko, took a small Petrushka. I put my hand."⁴

This campaign of I. Rubets to Kamchatka by B. Polevoy took place in 1662. He writes that: "... in the past in Yakutsk there were undoubtedly some documents about this campaign" [12]. S. Dezhnev returned from Anadyr to Yakutsk in 1658 and probably brought with him information about the wealth of Kamchatka "koshloks and beavers," because Yakut officials directly indicated in the letter of order to I. Rubets to beat "beavers and koshloks"⁵ [12]. As we mentioned above, in his above petition from 1667, I. Rubets directly called the Aikuel River - Kamchatka, as the already established official name of the river. The historian B. Polevoy did not pay attention to three essential facts in the above document: the "little Koryak" was a Russian hair, he did not know what his name was "in Koryak" and did not know his age. In connection with the above, a number of questions arise: 1) how the Koryaks end-

² Corrected from "took" according to what was written

³ Added to the line.

⁴ Transcription from Old Russian cursive writing was carried out by SP Konoplev A.G. The original text is attached. See Appendix 1.

⁵ Young beavers were called koshlok at that time. Due to the fact that there were no beavers in the North, they ceased to be mentioned in the mandate memos, but reappeared in the mandate memory of I. Rubets. Later, only Kamchatka sea beavers were called koshlok [12].

ed up on the Kamchatka River, it is known that Itelmens (Kamchadals) lived along this river; 2) how the Koryak boy had blond hair; 3) why he did not know his age and his Koryak name.

We found conjectural answers to all three of these questions:

1). The usual route of nomadic reindeer herds in North-Eastern Siberia is the same everywhere: in summer they wander from the midges to the sea, and in winter to the forest zone from a blizzard (I started my labor activity as a district doctor in the Zapolyarny settlement of Naiba on the Laptev Sea coast, and I know about it firsthand [14]). So, at that time, probably, the Koryaks wandered in the summer to the shore of the Bering Sea, and in the winter to the forest zone to Kamchatka, reaching the Kamchatka River. In the summer of 1654 S. Dezhnev "won" the Yakut woman from the merchant Popov from the Koryaks on the seashore, we wrote about this above, and in 1662, in a pogrom in winter or autumn, I. Rubets took the fair-haired Petrushka, probably from the same Koryaks on the Kamchatka river. Thus, we assume that Petrushka is the son of Fedot Popov. It is interesting if his mother, a Yakut, "won" in 1654 from the Koryaks, recognized her son if she was in the Anadyr prison, or if Dezhnev brought her to the city of Yakutsk by Semeyka, and they parted ways. It should be noted that women's hands were undoubtedly needed in the Anadyr prison, so she must have been there, if she had not died before that time (she must have been there, we will talk about this below). Could she tell the tithe's manager Ivashko

Rubets that "Petrushka is her son," if he considered him as his own? Of course not.

2). Among the Itelmens and Koryaks at that time there were no persons with light brown hair. Therefore, fair-haired Petrushka is undoubtedly the son of fair-haired Russian servicemen or industrial people. We do not know what kind of hair the merchant Fedot Popov had. So, the age of this Koryak boy - if he was born in 1650, then by 1662, he would have turned 12 years old, and by 1669 - already 19 years old, and, of course, this is no longer suitable for the Koryak "small" (ie, a minor), but it is quite suitable for Fedot Popov's son from his "Yakut woman". All adult non-baptized foreigners had to pay taxes, so age is of great importance. Petrushka was not very tall, so they confined themselves to answering the question: "And how old he was during the pogrom, he didn't remember that," although they were surprised that: "... And to this day he has not been baptized" [13] ...

3). Fair-haired Petrushka really did not know his name and age, if his father died when he was not even a year old, and his mother was lost at 4-5 years old. In another petition, the Koryak boy, Chakiiko, not only knew his name, but also his age - 16 years old, and he said that his father was killed by the Cossacks during the pogrom [15].

Thus, we come to the conclusion that the events written by G. Miller, described in the legends about "Fedotkin's son", and the fact that Fedot Popov's people reached the Kamchatka River, were probably in reality. This means that our hypothesis that the river was named Kam-

chatka from the word "khamcha", pronounced by a Yakut woman⁶, the wife of the merchant Fedot Popov, from amazement at the sight of the steaming hill Klyuchevskaya⁷, when they sailed along an unknown river, has the right to be. We need to clarify some doubts: 1) how could Fedot Popov's people sail along the Kamchatka River if the northern rivers freeze early, and the Dezhnev Family and Fedot Popov lost each other after the Protection of the Virgin (October 1); 2) why the activity of the Klyuchevskaya volcano can coincide, precisely when the Popov - Ankinov kochi were floating along the river, because volcanoes do not often erupt; 3) in 1647 whether the word "khamsa" (smoking pipe) was known to the Yakuts.

From Semyon Dezhnev's formal reply, it is clear that the ships of Fedot Alekseev Popov and Dezhnev "... went missing at sea" between September 20 and October 1 [16]. Further, the Dezhnev Semeyka reports: "And the Semeyka carried me along the sea after the Protection of the Virgin,⁸ went involuntarily everywhere and threw me ashore at the front end of the Onandyr River," that is, south of the mouth of the Anadyr River. Further, he writes that "... but there were all 25 of us on board, and we all went up the hill,⁹ we do not know our own paths, cold and hungry, naked and barefoot. And I, poor Semeyka, walked with my comrades to the Onandyr River equal to 10 weeks, and arrived at the Onandyr River down near the sea, and could not catch fish, there was no forest "[8]. Judging by this record, Semeyka with fellow travelers was thrown between Cape Navarin

⁶ The emotional response from surprise or sudden insight is usually accompanied by a cry. As the legend says - Archimedes, while taking a bath, suddenly discovered one of the basic laws of hydrostatics and, supposedly with a cry "Eureka", jumped out of the bath and ran naked. The people in such cases say: "cry out in surprise."

⁷ At first glance, the steaming hill Klyuchevskaya undoubtedly resembles smoke from tobacco smoldering in a smoking pipe.

⁸ 1st of October.

⁹ To go uphill means to go by land, by the coast, and not by the sea.

and Olyutorsky, most likely closer to Dezhnev Bay. They reached the mouth of the Anadyr River along the bank in 10 weeks. Fedot Popov himself is from the Pomors, and the Pomors were avid sailors, so his ship, probably, did not crash and sailed safely to the first big river on their way. According to long-term observations of hydrologists on the Kamchatka River: "The first ice phenomena (banks, sludge) appear in late October - early November. In mid-November, the river is covered with continuous freeze" [17]. If Semeyka Dezhnev and Fedot Alekseev parted in early October, then until mid-November there is enough time to travel to the Kamchatka River. If, according to Semeyka Dezhnev: "And I will voluntarily run from the Nose to the Anandira River for three days," then from their crash site to Kamchatka, at least 10 days will be enough, and maximum - 20 days of sailing. From the Kamchatka River, you can see the Klyuchevskaya Volcano, which is considered one of the most active volcanoes. Its eruptions occur at intervals from one year to 5-9 years [18]. The height of the hill is 4800 m, and it is already visible from the mouth of the Kamchatka River. On the first images of Kamchatka on the maps of Siberia, they wrote about this: "... and a stone pillar emerged from the sea opposite the mouth of the Kamchatka River, it is high without measure, and no one has been on it" [1]. Clouds of vapors and gases swirl without ceasing over its summit during the period of extinction of activity, the so-called, fumarole phenomenon. When there is no wind, they rise to the sky in a column. Series of eruptions in the so-called eruptive cycles "in some

cases can last for a long time: up to two or three years, and sometimes more" [18]. Therefore, the likelihood that Popov's companion Ankinidova saw the steaming hill Klyuchevskaya is very high.

Smoking was invented by the American Indians 1000-2000 BC. Tobacco was brought to Europe by Christopher Columbus from Cuba in 1492. The first tobacco plantation was established in 1531 in Spain. And in Russia tobacco appeared under Ivan the Terrible (1533 - 1584). In 1634, tobacco was banned in Russia by the decree of "the great sovereign tsar and great prince Mikhail Feodorovich of all Russia." The decree was confirmed in Moscow by 315 deputies of the Zemsky Cathedral in the Cathedral Code of 1649: "And who the Russian people and foreigners learn to keep tobacco, or learn how to trade in tobacco, and those people, sellers and merchants, were ordered to take and send them to the New Quarter, and for that the people were inflicted with a punishment with a great devil of mercy, under the death penalty, and having their yards and their bellies, sold, and put money into the sovereign's treasury" [19]. The Yakutsk prison was founded in 1632, and tobacco managed to spread in Yakutia. The smoking pipe first began to spread in Siberia at the beginning of the 17th century among the Chulym Turks from Bukhara merchants [20] and among Daur from China [21]. It is known that the Yakuts lived in the neighborhood with the Daur and conducted constant trade with them, even before the arrival of Russian servicemen. According to archaeologists in Yakutia, "... in burials of the 17th - 18th centuries. Smoking pipes

are found quite regularly" [22]. The etymology of the word "khamsa" in the BTSYA (Comprehensive Explanatory Dictionary of the Yakut Language) is explained as a derivative from the Middle Mongolian and Turkic word gangza, the Tibetan gangzag (smoking pipe) [23]. Thus, the word "khamsa" was known to the Sakha (Yakuts) from the beginning of the 17th century.

The further fate of the Yakut wife of the merchant Fedot Alekseev Popov is unknown. Apparently, she stayed to live in the Anadyr prison and left her offspring. Ten kilometers higher from the prison along the Anadyr River, later, the settlement of Markovo was founded, and among the inhabitants of this settlement there are descendants of the inhabitants of the Anadyr prison, founded by Semeika Dezhnev in 1649. Wikipedia says: "By the end of the 19th century, the permanent population of Markovo reached 250 people who called themselves Chuvans, speaking the Old Russian dialect, converted to Orthodoxy, observed both church and pagan rituals" [24]. We compared the mitochondrial genome of residents with Markovo and Koryak with mitochondrial genomes of Sakha women¹⁰ and found two minimally different genomes. The mitochondrial genome of the Koryak from the Karaginsky district of the Koryak Autonomous Okrug of Kamchatka [25] differs from the complete mitogenome of Sakha by two mutations in the HVSII region at positions 248 and 249 [26], and the mitochondrial genome of the Even from the village. Markovo [25] also differs by two mutations in the hypervariable region¹¹ from the Sakha mitogenome of the Ver-

¹⁰ The mitochondrial genome is passed only through the maternal line from mother to children, and then it is passed only from daughter to her children, and so on. Sons do not pass on mtDNA to their children.

khoyansk ulus [26]. Even from the village of Markovo there is probably a descendant of later settlers, while the Koryak may be a descendant of earlier settlers, or vice versa.

Thus, we believe that the hypothesis of A. N. Bondareva receives new confirmation and refinement by the results of our research. As A. N. Bondareva rightly notes: “Even if, after Plevoy, we admit that in the years 1660/61, it was Chukichev with Kamchaty (and not in the 40s Fedot Popov) who reached Nikulka and wintered there, then on the way back

all of them were killed in their winter quarters in the upper reaches of the Gizhiga (Chendon). Who named the river after Kamchaty and who reported a new toponym to Yakutsk, if the Yukaghirs killed the entire detachment without exception (11 people)?! And this was not revealed immediately. This is not the only vulnerable spot in Plevoy's hypothesis, which, in principle, is the most endearing of all known to us “[4]. The Yakut word “Khamchaakky”, or “Khamchaaki” (the Yakut pronunciation of the name of Kamchatka),

which is often used in folklore, apparently appeared in it from the stories of service people, and it cannot be ruled out from Dezhnev Semeyka himself, because he was twice married to Yakuts. In our opinion, the origins of the name of Kamchatka are in the Yakut word “khamcha”, pronounced by a Yakut woman, the wife of the merchant Popov, in the folk, not literary dialect “khamcha”. The name of our hero remains unknown, but his memory remains in the name of the river and the Kamchatka peninsula.

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¹¹ The hypervariable area of the mitogenome is the area that is subject to very frequent mutations, therefore the divergence of Kamchatka and Anadyr women from Yakuts occurred not so long ago.

Appendix 1. Original petition from foreman Ivan Rubets

a)

b)

d)

c)

Appendix 1. The original of the petition of the Cossack Ivan Rubets (RGADA; Fund 1171 Yakutsk clerk hut; Inventory No. 3 part 3; File 1691. Yakutsk, 1669. L. 138-139): a) sheet 138; b) the reverse side of sheet 138; c) sheet 139; d) reverse side of sheet 139.

REFERENCES

1. Polevoy B.P. Novoe ob otkrytii Kamchatki [New about the discovery of Kamchatka]. V. 1. Petropavlovsk-Kamchatskij: Kamchatskij pechatnyj dvor, 1997. 167 p. (In Russian).
2. Burykin A.A. Istoriya otkrytiya Kamchatki ili bajki starogo Paratuna? Domysly, vymysly i umysly v ob"yasnenii proiskhozhdeniya nazvaniya «Kamchatka» (po materialam knigi B.P. Polevogo «Novoe ob otkrytii Kamchatki»)[History of the discovery of Kamchatka or the tales of old Paratun? Speculation, inventions and intentions in explaining the origin of the name "Kamchatka" (based on the book by B.P. Polevoy "New about the discovery of Kamchatka")] // Sibirskaya zaimka. 2013(in Russian).
3. ZHilin M. Otkuda u Kamchatki imya? [Where does Kamchatka get its name?] // Slovesnica Iskusstv. 2015. № 2. P. 124–130. (In Russian).
4. Bondareva A.N. Fol'klornye istoki nazvaniya Kamchatki (novaya gipoteza) [Folklore origins of the name of Kamchatka (new hypothesis)] // Kraevedcheskie zapiski Kamchatskogo oblastnogo kraevedcheskogo muzeya. 1973. № 4. P. 147–158. (In Russian).
5. Pekarskij E.K. Slovar' yakutskogo yazyka [Dictionary of the Yakut language]. T. 3. 2-e izd. Moskva: AN SSSR, 1959. 3291 p. (In Russian).
6. Bol'shoj tolkovyj slovar' yakutskogo yazyka [Comprehensive explanatory dictionary of the Yakut language]. T. 13 / pod red. Slepcev P.A. Novosibirsk: Nauka, 2016. 680 p. (In Russian).
7. Miller G.F. Opisanie morskikh puteshestvij po Ledovitomu i po Vostochnomu moryu, s Rossijskoj storony uchinennyh. // Sochineniya po istorii Rossii. Izbrannoe. Moskva: Nauka, 1996. P. 25–26. (In Russian).
8. Dezhnev S.I. Podlinnye dokumenty o plavanii S. I. Dezhneva № 1 [Authentic documents about S. I. Dezhnev's voyage No. 1] [Elektronnyj resurs] // F. YAkutskaya prikaznaya izba, on. 3, 1656 r., № 18. 1656. C. лл. 2-4. URL: https://drevlit.ru/docs/russia/XVII/1640-1660/Dezhnev_S_I/text1.php (accessed: 13.10.2021). (In Russian).
9. Spasskij G.I. Istoriya plavanij rossiyan iz rek Sibirskih v Ledovitoe more [The history of the voyages of Russians from Siberian rivers to the Arctic Sea] // Sibirskij Vestnik. Sanktpeterburg: izd. G.Spasskogo, 1821. V. Ч. 15. 17 p. (In Russian).
10. Efimov A.V. Iz istorii velikih geograficheskikh otkrytij [From the history of great geographical discoveries]. Moskva: Nauka, 1971. 300 p. (In Russian).
11. Krasheninnikov S. Opisanie zemli Kamchatki sochinennoe Stepanom Krasheninnikovym, Akademii nauk professorom [Description of the land of Kamchatka by Stepan Krasheninnikov, Professor of the Academy of Sciences]. Sankt Peterburg: Imperatorskaya Akademiya nauk, 1755. 126 p. (In Russian).
12. Polevoj B.P. Novoe ob otkrytii Kamchatki [New about the discovery of Kamchatka]. V. 2. Petropavlovsk-Kamchatskij: Kamchatskij pechatnyj dvor, 1997. 203 p. (In Russian).
13. Rubec I.M. 1668-1669 gg (7177 g. sentyabr'-iyunya). Dela po chelobitnym desyatnika I.M. Rubca [Cases on petitions of the foreman I.M. Rubets]... // RGADA; Fond 1171 YAkutskaya prikaznaya izba; Opis' №3 chast' 3; Delo 1691. YAkutsk, 1669. P. 138–139. (In Russian).
14. Tikhonov D.G. Zapiski uchastkovogo vracha iz Zapolyar'ya [Notes of the district doctor from the Arctic] // YAkutskij medicinskij zhurnal. 2004. № 3. P. 35–37. (In Russian).
15. Kondrat'ev I. 1668-1669 gg (7177 g. sentyabr'-iyunya). Dela po chelobitnym desyatnika I.M. Rubca [Cases on petitions of the foreman I.M. Rubets] ... // RGADA; Fond 1171 YAkutskaya prikaznaya izba; Opis' №3 chast' 3; Delo 1691. Moskva: RGADA, 1669. P. 143–158. (In Russian).
16. Podlinnye dokumenty o plavanii S. I. Dezhneva [Authentic documents about S.I.Dezhnev's voyage] // Russkie arkticheskie ekspedicii XVII-XX vv. Voprosy istorii izucheniya i osvoeniya Arktiki. Leningrad: Gidrometeorologicheskoe izdatel'stvo, 1964. P. 133–143. (In Russian).
17. Bonk A.A. Harakteristika Presnovodnyh Vodoemov Kamchatki [Characteristics of Kamchatka Freshwater Reservoirs]. Petropavlovsk-Kamchatskij: Vsemirnyj fond dikoj prirody, 2015. 52 p. (In Russian).
18. Pijp B.I. Osobennosti izverzheniya Klyuchevskoj sopki [Features of the eruption of Klyuchevskaya Sopka]. // Trudy laboratorii vulkanologii AN SSSR. 1958. № 13. P. 99–119. (In Russian).
19. Tihomirov, M.N. Epifanov P.P. Sobornoe Ulozhenie 1649 goda [Cathedral Code of 1649]

- [Electronic resources]. 1961. URL: <http://www.hist.msu.ru/ER/Etext/1649/whole.htm> (accessed: 14.10.2021). (In Russian).
20. Belikova O., Zinchenko A. Kuritel'nye aksesuary XVII-XIX vv. taezhnogo Prichulyum'ya (YUg Zapadnoj Sibiri): Trubki [Smoking accessories of the XVII-XX centuries. taiga near the Chulyum region (South of Western Siberia): Pipes]// Vestnik Arheologii, Antropologii I Etnografii. 2012. V. 17, № 2. P. 93–105. (In Russian).
 21. Shapovalov A.V. Tabak v Zapadnoj Sibiri v XVII-XVIII vv. [Tobacco in Western Siberia in the 17th-18th centuries]// CHuzhdoe - chuzhoe - nashe. Nablyudeniya k probleme vzaimodejstviya kul'tur. Novosibirsk, 2001. P. 107–121. (In Russian).
 22. Kir'yanov N.S. i dr. Nahodki na o. Kyllah v Olekminskom rajone respubliki Saha (Yakutiya) i perspektivy poiska yakutskih pogrebenij dohristsianskogo perioda v YUzhnoj YAKutii [Finds on the island of Kyllakh in the Olekminsky region of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia) and the prospects for the search for Yakut burials of the pre-Christian period in South Yakutia]// Izvestiya laboratorii drevnih tekhnologij. 2016. V. 21, № 4. P. 37–49. (In Russian).
 23. BТSYA. Bol'shoj tolkovyj slovar' yakutskogo yazyka [Comprehensive explanatory dictionary of the Yakut language] v 15 t., V. VII / pod red. Slepcev P.A. Novosibirsk: Nauka, 2010. 259 s. (In Russian).
 24. Vikipediya. Markovo (CHukotskij avtonomnyj okrug) [Markovo (Chukotka Autonomous District)] [Elektronnyj resurs]. 2021. URL: [https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Markovo_\(CHukotskij_avtonomnyj_okrug\)](https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Markovo_(CHukotskij_avtonomnyj_okrug)) (accessed: 14.10.2021). (In Russian).
 25. Dryomov S. V. и др. Mitochondrial genome diversity on the Central Siberian Plateau with particular reference to the prehistory of northernmost Eurasia // PLoS One. 2021. V. 16, № 1 January. P. 1–18.
 26. Duggan A.T. и др. Investigating the prehistory of Tungusic peoples of Siberia and the Amur-Ussuri region with complete mtDNA genome sequences and Y-chromosomal markers // PLoS One. 2013. V. 8, № 12. P. 1–19.

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